

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

<https://llrjournal.com/index.php/11>

**A CRITICAL EXPLORATION OF GREEN CONTENTS AND
ECOLOGICAL AWARENESS IN SECONDARY-LEVEL ENGLISH
TEXTBOOKS OF PUNJAB, PAKISTAN**

Komal Sajjad¹ Dr. Mujahid Abbas²

¹MS English Linguistics (Scholar), Department of Humanities, COMSATS University Islamabad, Vehari Campus, Pakistan.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Humanities, COMSATS University Islamabad, Vehari Campus, Pakistan

¹mujahid@cuivehari.edu.pk,

²komalsajjad114@gmail.com

Abstract

This research is conducted to explore the issues of ecological awareness that are presented in green content of secondary-level English textbooks in Punjab, Pakistan. The prominent issues like climate change, pollution, and depletion of forest resources, education is essential in nurturing the ecological literacy and sustainable ideals in young learners. This research focused on the green content in the English textbooks recommended by Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board in cultivating environmental awareness among the students in the secondary level. Qualitative research is appropriate for this study because it allows the researcher to explore how the environmental themes are represented, depicted, and framed in the context of the chosen textbooks. The research employs Ecological Discourse Analysis proposed by Charles J. Fillmore (1993) to systematically analyze the Grade 9 and Grade 10 English textbooks. The study identifies and examines environmental and eco-friendly themes found in reading passages, poems, essays, and comprehension texts. The study creates an emphasis on the possibility of the use of the English language education as a transformative factor in ensuring sustainable development and ecological responsibility of future citizens.

Keywords:

Ecological Awareness, Green Content, English Textbooks, Ecological Discourse Analysis

INTRODUCTION

The global environmental issues that are facing the world today in the twenty-first century are difficult to such a level that it has put the survival of humans, social stability and economic prosperity of the whole world at stake. These problems are ingrained in social practices, cultural values, political decisions, and communication and require the global consciousness, education, and sustainability responsibility (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 2022, pp. 5-10). Although Pakistan contributes low global emissions, this country is highly susceptible to the effects of climate change such as an increase in temperature, unpredictable rainfall, floods, droughts, pollution and deforestation. Informal education prepares students to read social realities, participate in the world and anticipate citizenship roles.

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a good measure of environmental sustainability as a sustainability issue on the global level. In 2015, the SDGs have been adopted, and the importance of integrated approaches to address the social, economic, and environmental concerns is emphasized. This research work is directly related to SDG 4 (Quality Education) that emphasizes the importance of education in achieving sustainable development (Ramzan et al., 2025, 2023, 2020), global citizenship (Akram & Yang, 2021; Akram, 2020), as well as environmental awareness. It is also closely connected with SDG 13 (Climate Action), which calls to

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

the immediate reaction to the issue of climate change founded on education, awareness, and capacity building. This research considers itself to be part of a world agenda; it determines the green content in English textbooks in secondary level in Punjab, Pakistan, because education is considered one of the main sources of sustainability. Although there has been increased awareness of the role of environmental education, ecological education in the school curriculum in Pakistan. In the secondary level, English textbooks are recommended by Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board (PCTB) include the selected texts which inform about nature, environmental issues and human concern to the environment. In the absence of such an analysis, it cannot be determined whether these textbooks are making a significant contribution towards environmental literacy, or simply introduce ecological content in a narrow way. The importance of this research is that it has the potential to be applied in academic research as well as education. Academically, it attempts to fill a gap in literature since it concentrates on ecological discourse in English textbooks in the Pakistani context. Although there is international research on the effectiveness of language education in facilitating environmental awareness. To address this issue, the current research paper engaged in a rigorous search of green content of high-school level English textbooks that are being used in Punjab, Pakistan. This research is expected to work towards the greater objective of ensuring sustainable development via education by illuminating the use of English language textbook in creating environmental awareness amongst the students about their role to the natural world around them.

Research Questions

1. How does the green content given in English textbooks at the secondary level contribute to developing ecological awareness among secondary-level learners in Punjab, Pakistan?
2. What environmental issues and eco-friendly themes are represented in the green content of English textbooks?

Literature Review

The study is within the scope of the existing knowledge, find trends in methodologies, theoretical framework, and gaps that cannot be closed, and justify the need to conduct new inquiry (Booth et al., 2016, pp.). 15-22). Environmental education research reviews not only have been able to give a mapping of the impact of the textbook and the curriculum on ecological attitudes, but have also provided evidence of ideological bias, pedagogical deficiencies and possible transformative interventions. This long analysis is based on diversity of global and Pakistani backgrounds to emphasize the evolving debate on ecolinguistics, integrating sustainability and citizenship formation.

Ishaque et al. (2025) undertook qualitative content analysis of teacher education curriculum of teacher education institutes of Pakistan in light of theory of EE based on Orr (1992), and sustainability models. The authors propose curricular reforms emphasizing experiential education as a means of preparing teachers for Pakistan, a country prone to climate change, where the need for proactive sustainability thinking becomes more urgent with rising temperatures and floods (Ishaque et al., 2025, pp. 45-60). Khan, Salman and Naz (2025) investigated the Grade 6-8 English textbooks of government schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa with the Ecofeminist-ecolinguistic approach and critical discourse analysis. The materials should be updated with a focus on bio centric ethics, integration of indigenous knowledge and empowerment of young learners in biodiversity hotspots

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

(Khan et al., 2025, p.). 75-92). The ideological bias was in favor of industrialization rather than equity and the experiential ideology of pedagogy was discovered in line with the index of vulnerability of Pakistan (Sindh Textbook Board, 2024, pp. 110-135). In the research of green discourses, Abbas & Rasheed (2024) applied the theories of Stibbe (2015) and Barthes (1968) of the domain of Eco linguistics and semiology respectively to analyze the green discourses in the primary English/Urdu edition of Punjab Textbook Board (2022-2023). This makes textbooks one of the sources to embed behaviour for long term learning ideologically. (Abbas & Rasheed, 2024, pp. 65-85). This leaves a vacuum between discursive representations and actual ecological change, and does not fully address an investigation of behavioral change.

Afzal, Nayab and Noor (2024) compared Punjab Board and Oxford secondary English texts with the Hallidayan transitivity and EDA by employing Single National Curriculum of Pakistan . Thematic distinctions illuminate the publishers' ideology that influences the eco-attitudes (Afzal et al., 2024, pp. 88-105). The top down depiction without interactivity and locality was observed in social studies books whereas global warming was observed as a theoretical universality in the books evaluated by Seker (2024) Eco linguistically. Contextual, participative tools with requests are appealing to the aspirations of Pakistan (Seker, 2024, pp. 120-140)

In the quasi-experiment study by Telešienė et al. (2024), the author set the pre and post questionnaires for a sustainability course at a Lithuanian university and controls. Experimental gains on responsibility and pro-behavior were confirmed to be valid to structured interventions to leadership (Telešienė et al., 2024, pp.). 150-175). The results of the survey conducted by Indriyani et al. (2023) on 251 Indonesian students, who did the ecology-infused language tasks, confirmed that there were twofold benefits of proficiency and multiliteracy to global action (Indriyani et al., 2023, pp.). 195-215). Hnatyuk et al. (2024) assessed the attitudes of 453 Ukrainian students of different disciplines, revealing a discrepancy in engagement but even awareness, indicating that education is stimulating participation without a certain change (Hnatyuk et al., 2024, pp.). 142-160). Imran et al. (2024) in their ecolanguage analysis of SNC Grade 7-8 ELT units of smog/planting in Pakistan with Stibbe (2015) and Orr (1992) praises the remedial framings of elementary literacy (Imran et al., 2024, pp.). 200-225). These texts elucidate how textbooks exercise discursive power in frames of ecology of anthropocentrism to citizenship, but reveals unmet gaps: theoretical preeminence, cultural irrelevance and action-centricity especially in Pakistan. The following research have to concentrate on the longitudinal effects and physical-digital pedagogies (Alsaleh, 2025, pp.). 876-884). The articles by Aurélio et al. (2023) and Lee and Kang (2023) demonstrate that using child-friendly literatures on ecology can develop transformative environmental citizenship and reinforce constraining anthropocentric ideologies with the help of minor linguistic and narrative decisions (Aurélio et al., 2023, pp.). 112-125; Lee & Kang, 2023, pp. 78-92).

Aurélio et al. (2023) studied a children book intervention on river basin ecology on 176 primary students in different urban, coastal, public and private schools in Brazil. With a sequential explanatory mixed-method, where pre/ after-tests were conducted to assess the level of awareness and behaviors, and focus groups, the research anchored its discussion on the notion of environmental literacy and ecological citizenship. These theories suppose that literacy is a multifaceted synthesis of knowledge, attitudes, skills, and behaviors and citizenship involves people actively participating in ethical activism to conserve the ecosystem (Aurélio et al., 2023, pp.). 115-118). This was echoed by Cristovao (2022) in Brazilian EFL materials as at times environmental units are not holistically deep (just mentioned, not converted into behavioral change of eco-literacy

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

as proposed by Stibbe, 2015, and Orr, 1992), which makes such environmental units superficial in nature (Cristovao, 2022, pp.). 45-58). Alabaş and Akagunduz (2021) have conducted a systematic review of Turkish geography curriculum/textbooks (Grades 9-12), integrating environmental ethics with the ecolinguistics approach of Stibbe to unveil balanced anthropocentric/eco-centric orientations focusing on the sustainability pillars of stewardship and nature-love (Alabaş and Akagunduz, 2021, pp.). 201-215). Biström and Lundström (2021) criticized Swedish compulsory-school ELT as greenwashed, i.e. superficial sustainability without critical analysis, in spite of the ecolinguistic promise (Biström and Lundström, 2021, pp.). 67-78). Hookoomsing and Oozeerally (2020) revealed subtle anthropocentrism in Mauritian Grade 3 ELT through the discourse analysis, in which the image/texts were visualizing the exploitation unintentionally rather than the eco-centric harmony (Hookoomsing & Oozeerally, 2020, pp.). 89-102). Zahoor and Janjua (2020) confirmed the ecolinguistic potential of Pakistani primary ELT in accordance with Stibbe (2015) and Hall (1997), in which conscious vocabulary/narratives develop awareness, and consciously use language to promote ecological well-being (Zahoor and Janjua, 2020, pp.). 156-168). The knowledge-based ELT misalignments in Indonesia/Spain with SDG-based transformative goals were critiqued by Zulfiani et al. and Martinez and Torres (2021, pp. 110-122; Martinez & Torres, 2021, pp. (95-108) .Wangid (2018) experimentally confirmed the effectiveness of science-math storybooks in Grade 4 environmental gain through constructivism, and it was more effective than controls (Wangid, 2018, pp.). 301-315). From these gaps the need for new research is evident. The importance of adopting mixed-methods and longitudinal approaches to future research is highlighted to explore not only the processes of ecological meaning construction but also their implications for future learners' attitudes, identities and behaviors over time. The combination of Eco linguistics and multimodal discourse analysis and CDA can provide more insights into the interaction of language, visuals and social practices in terms of how they contribute to ecological consciousness.

Research Methodology

This article focused on the role of green content in Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board (PCTB) English textbooks (Grades 9-10) in promoting ecological literacy among secondary level English Language Learners (ELLs) in Pakistan. This research adopts a qualitative methodology based on the Ecological Discourse Analysis (EDA) to explore the representation, construction, and expression of ecological ideas in linguistic to develop sustainable.

Ecological Discourse Analysis (EDA) is based on ecolinguistics, and was pioneered by Fillmore Fill (1993) who made language-ecology interconnections, and argued that discourse was a reflection and a representation of environmental perceptions. In textbooks, EDA shows how the English materials can have a two-fold linguistic-ideological role, conveying not only grammar, but preconditioned ecological attitudes (Gray, 2010, pp.). 45-52). In the case of Pakistan curriculum that focuses on civic-environmental responsibility, EDA evaluates the way PCTB texts promote eco-centric harmony or anthropocentric exploitation. EDA Application Dimensions.

- Linguistic Representations: Discusses pollution, deforestation, and climate representations, i.e. whether as a living system (eco-centric) or as human resources (anthropocentric). The scientific processes (water cycles, food chains) are a mixture of moral-scientific framing (Stibbe, 2015, pp. 67-78).

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- Ideological Positioning: Determines eco-centrism (all life is valued), anthropocentrism (human-centric), or sustainability (coexistence by balancing), and assesses whether the texts foster responsibility or marginalize ecology.
- Learner Impact: Measures discourse influences on attitudes, including sympathy, through metaphors of fragile nature, and utility through metaphors of resource.
- Curricular Alignment: Map content on ecological literacy objectives of Punjab National Curriculum as core or supplementary.

Textbooks in English Grades 9-10, compulsory in Punjab high schools, aim at adolescents (15-17) in the critical period of moral-environmental development. Sampling Criteria Intentional sampling of ecologically pertinent materials: natural resources, pollution, climate change, deforestation, conservation, and human - nature ethics. Units that compared the present practices with the sustainable principles took priority. This stratified method reveals explicit/implicit messages forming ecological awareness. The research demonstrates the unclear position of green content it exists but is ideologically subject to conditioning. This requires systematic integration of eco-discourse to achieve holistic knowledge, empathy and action literacy to develop environmentally responsible citizens of Pakistan (Stibbe, 2021, pp. 112-120).

Analysis

This research presented the environmental problem of climate change, deforestation, and pollution are portrayed in the Grade 9 and 10 English textbook (Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board) based on the Ecological Discourse Analysis (EDA). Based on Ecolinguistics as originally conceived by Alwin Fill and developed by Arran Stibbe, the analysis focus on how ordinary language in textbooks forms ecological ideologies and how it can influence the perceptions of learners towards the natural world. The framework by Stibbe and, in particular, the idea of the stories we live by, brings attention to the fact that discourse can either help instill the ideals of ecocentrism, i.e. the focus on care, empathy, and the need to take ecological balance into account, or reaffirm anthropocentric beliefs, which revolve around human needs instead of ecological balance.

Textbook: Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board (PCTB). English Book 9. Lahore: PCTB. Chapter 8: *Noise in the Environment* (Grade 9th English textbook)

“Let us promise to make our environment peaceful for ourselves and for others.”

Based on Arran Stibbe Eco linguistic framework, where everyday language in texts creates ecological ideologies, and defines how learners perceive the environment (Li & Akram, 2023, 2024), the following sentence in a paragraph format of Unit 8: Noise in the Environment (Grade 9 English textbook, Page 103, Let us promise to make our environment peaceful to ourselves and to others) can be analyzed in a paragraph format:

The line is written in an inclusive and action oriented language to engage the learners directly in environmental responsibility. Such expressions as let us promise, for us and others and others make up a group responsibility where it is a collective moral and social responsibility to ensure that an environment of peace exists. This is eco-centric linguistically because it is clear that care about the environment and wellbeing of all living things is a foregrounding discourse unlike a human need centric discourse.

The ideological position that the statement is propagating is that of sustainability and stewardship whereby students are actively expected to think about the effects of their behaviors on their

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

environment. It contributes to human responsibility in curbing the environment such as noise pollution and conservation of ecological balance by connecting the human behavior to environmental peace. The wording has the spirit of empathy, collaboration and respecting nature. The overall impact on learners, the commanding and encouragement tone will most probably encourage loyalty, moral thought, and active attitude toward building a harmonious environment. This is in accordance with the goals of Punjab National Curriculum to develop civic responsibility, environmental awareness, and ecological literacy, which indicate that the sphere of textbook discussion may influence student attitudes and behaviors in relation to sustainable practices

Chapter 10: The Silent Predator and the Majestic Prey Snow Leopard and Markhor (Grade 9th English textbook)

“However, human activities have upset this delicate balance. Poaching, habitat destruction, and climate change have reduced populations of both the species.”

These lines illustrate the construction of ecological reality and shaping of ideological meanings through language. This discourse follows the concept of “stories we live by” by which Stibbe encourages an ecological responsibility narrative instead of one that is more human-centric. Exploitative human activity is indicated as the cause of the reduction in the population of species like the snow leopard and markhor, thus encouraging more sustainable thinking.

Ideologically, evaluative language like ‘upset’ and ‘reduced’ has negative connotations that affect the learners’ emotional connection and moral stance towards environmental issues. This evaluative language has a large impact on influencing the attitudes and perceptions that learners hold about environmental degradation, which results in their seeing it as an ethical issue, and not as a non-issue or inevitable occurrence.

More importantly, the discourse also promotes ecological awareness, whereby the learners are aware and conscious of the relations between human actions and environmental consequences. It aims to raise awareness of the fragility of ecosystems, of endangered species and to promote a better understanding of biodiversity conservation. The awareness is important in the Pakistani context as wildlife protection is a timely issue and it is important to create informed and responsible citizens. The ecosystem is portrayed as fragile and in need of care and sustainability. The overall tone of the discourse is an eco-centric one, which questions anthropocentric concepts and suggests that man should have moral and practical obligations to ensure protection and sustainability of the natural environment.

Chapter 10: The Silent Predator and the Majestic Prey (Grade 9th English textbook)

“Poaching and habitat destruction have led to a decline in their numbers.”

In the context of the Eco linguistic approach proposed by Arran Stibbe, where the analysis of common language reveals the ideologies behind the environment and how it represents the learner’s perceptions, the line clearly emphasizes the effect of human activities, such as poaching and habitat destruction, on the environment. The relationship of cause and effect is direct and the verb phrase “leads to a decline” specifies the negative consequence of these actions and reinforces their severity. The sentence reflects an eco-centric ideology as it gives a value to the lives of the snow leopards and Markhors and at the same time emphasizes the negative impact of human interference. The discourse is implicit in its scope, implying a responsibility for human practices in environmental harm, thus questioning anthropocentric assumptions and gently advancing sustainability thinking.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Moreover, the line fosters ecological awareness by raising awareness among the learners of the relationship between human and biodiversity loss. It fosters awareness that endangered species are part of an ecosystem and not an add-on or a disposable part of it. It builds learners' awareness of the environmental problems and instills a sense of responsibility and values toward environmental conservation. Thus, the discourse is used pedagogically to develop information-providing attitudes and worldview of an environmentally sensitive one which strengthens the protection of ecological balance.

Chapter 5: The Rainforest (Grade 10th English Textbook)

“Rainforests are being cut down for timber and farming.”

Using the Eco linguistic framework proposed by Arran Stibbe, who focuses on the everyday language in a text as the construct of ecological ideologies and the attitude towards the environment it fosters in a learner, the following sentence of Unit 5: The Rainforest (Grade 9 English textbook, Page 66, Rainforests are being cut down for timber and farming) in its paragraph form:

The line distinctly talks of the continued destruction of rainforests, with a direct relation to the human activity of harvesting timber and farming. The passive voice in the sentence, are being cut down puts more stress on the action being performed to the forest than the actors, covertly showing the rainforest as an at-risk system. In terms of EDA, this is eco-centric discourse, as it throws emphasis on ecological damage of the same human exploitation and conservation of such ecosystems.

The sentence has an ideological meaning that conveys a message on issues of environment contrary to anthropocentric perspective. The text invites the learners to comprehend the impacts of economic human activities on biodiversity and ecological balance by giving the names of the main causes of deforestation, timber and farming. It is through this framing that we have created awareness of sustainability and conservation as a social and ethical obligation.

Concerning its impact on the learners, the language can be used in the form of a worry about the rainforest and the creatures living in it, which creates ecological empathy and stewardship. It helps students to think about how human activities can affect the ecosystem and it builds ecological literacy. Moreover, the information fits into the purpose of the Punjab National Curriculum which is to incorporate ecological knowledge into the school curriculum and show how ecological knowledge could be integrated into subject learning to develop responsible attitudes towards the environment.

The line emphasizes the destruction of rainforests that are caused by humans, and portrays them as something that needs safeguarding. It encourages the eco-centric values through EDA through highlighting the impact of timber extraction and farming on the biodiversity. The language stimulates learners to be eco-empathetic and have a feeling of being a steward. In general, it is consistent with the objectives of the Punjab National Curriculum that help to raise environmental consciousness and develop responsible behavior towards the environment.

Chapter 8: Peace (Grade 10th English Textbook)

"The wind is now a roaring, smashing monster of destruction, raking all man's work from the valleys, from the vales"

Using the Eco linguistic framework proposed by Arran Stibbe, who focuses on the everyday language in a text as the construct of ecological ideologies and the attitude towards the environment

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

it fosters in a learner, the wind is now a roaring, smashing monster of destruction, raking all man's work from the valleys, from the vales is an example of the ecological (eco-stylistic) model, where nature is a strong, active destructive force, which disrupts the life of man. The wind is not defined as a neutral element of environment, but as an agent involved in material processes of "roaring," "smashing" and "raking." These action verbs create the wind as the lead actor, whereas 'all man's work' turns into the victim, revealing the vulnerability of the human being. Ecologically this represents the natural forces over man's efforts to control it.

In this case, the metaphor 'monster of destruction' is essential to the creation of a representation of nature in the ecological (eco-stylistic) model. The wind is personified, giving it a monstrous identity, making it a threatening, almost intentional destroyer. This figurative architecture displays an anthropocentric perspective that considers nature as being antagonistic to humanity in the event that it endangers its stability. The language of the wind is one that sees it not as a part of the natural ecological system; rather, it sees wind as an enemy, a product of human fear and lack of control over the forces of nature.

Choices of lexis and sound patterns enhance the image of destruction and reinforce the ecological meaning in the context of the ecological (eco-stylistic) model. The use of words like "roaring" and "smashing" are meant to suggest sound and physical violence, and the repetition is designed to convey the wide extent of the devastation. All these features contribute to the overall feeling of environmental disruptions, implying a reach of nature's force on every landscape. This foregrounding of style is a means of making the magnitude and potential of ecological power visible.

The ecological (eco-stylistic) model brings the ideological aspects of the lineup, thus commenting on the interaction between man and nature in greater depth. The phrase "all man's work" represents human civilization, effort and control, which are demonstrated to be ephemeral and precariously fragile in the presence of nature. The wind's power of "raking" implies the supremacy of nature and the idea of man's superiority is in question. In this way, the text has a message of ecological warning: it is a reminder of the limits of human power in nature and of the importance of being humble and aware of them.

Chapter 12: Population Growth and World Food Supplies (Grade 10th English Textbook)

"Great pressure is being placed on arable land, water, energy, and biological resources. As the world population grows, the food problem will become increasingly severe."

Using the Eco linguistic framework proposed by Arrant Stibbe, who focuses on the everyday language in a text as the construct of ecological ideologies and the attitude towards the environment it fosters in a learner, By using Ecological model, the above claim "Great pressure is being placed on arable land, water, energy and biological resources" is unsympathetic to the environment, interpreting it as resources that are being put under strain. When using the passive construction "is being placed", it gives no clear indication of who is responsible for ecological degradation. The listed elements, however, are part of a range of semantic equivalents related to essential life support systems, highlighting the importance of these elements to human life and ecological balance. This building illustrates the heightened importance placed on natural systems and the tendency to de-emphasize the role of human activity in environmental conversations.

The ecological (eco-stylistic) model is used to metaphorically represent environmental exploitation as a burden on nature by choosing the lexical item "pressure". Metaphorical expression of overuse,

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

strain and possible failure of the environment, as if it is being pushed. An anthropocentric discourse pattern is strengthened by the lack of explicit human actors, with the consequences of human action being highlighted, but the responsibility is distributed. So the language reflects a loss of the ecological balance with too few resources and overuse.

In the second sentence, "As the world population grows, the food problem will become increasingly severe," a causal relationship between the two is drawn using the ecological (eco-stylistic) model. "World population" is emphasized as the stimulus in the clause structure and "food problem" is presented as a consequence. The comparative form of "increasingly severe" further enhances the sense of urgency and imminent crisis, indicating that environmental and food security issues are likely to become more severe over time if the trend persists. The ecological (eco-stylistic) model gives the ideological meaning of the combination of these statements warning about the surroundings and the general state of the world. The text builds a story about the expansion of the human population exerting an unsustainable pressure on ecosystems, which may result in food and resource shortages and crises. It brings together the issues of human development and environmental sustainability in an implicit demand for responsible use of resources. In general, the statements foster an ecological awareness that emphasizes the boundaries of natural resources and the need to respond to the imbalance between human demands and the environment's carrying capacity.

Conclusion

In conclusion language is very important in the creation of ecological ideologies and the perspective of learners on the natural world in the selected teaching text of grade 10 English. The use of the Eco linguistic approach proposed by Arran Stubbe makes it clear that nature is presented as a force that is very powerful, uncontrollable and destructive in Chapter 8: Peace. The wind, described as a "roaring, smashing monster of destruction," becomes a metaphor for a living and threatening force that wreaks havoc on man's stability and effaces "all man's work." Such representation emphasizes the superiority of Nature to human activity and the precariousness of human achievements. The use of metaphor, personification and violent lexical items not only heightens the emotional experience of the text, but also contributes to the reinforcement of a worldview that places humans in conflict with the natural environment. Thus, learners are introduced to a discourse that recognizes the tremendous power of nature, also that there is an implicit fear and opposition to nature, but not a balanced or harmonious ecological relationship.

The chapter on Population Growth and World Food Supplies (Chapter 12) provides an analysis of another important ecological discourse, one that is based on resource scarcity and human pressure on natural systems. The use of passive construction in the statement "Great pressure is being placed on arable land, water, energy, and biological resources" makes it difficult to detect the human dimension and spreads the responsibility for exploitation of biological resources, energy, and water, and arable land. In the Arran Stubbe's Eco linguistic perspective, such decisions are important as they influence the learner's perception of ecological issues and their origins. The metaphoric "pressure" creates an environment as a burdened object that implies overuse and stress and is also a reinforcement of an anthropocentric vision where nature is presented as a group of resources for human beings. Furthermore, the causal connection between population growth and worsening of the food problem in the second sentence builds a sense of inevitability to the worsening food problem. This discourse addresses the urgency; it shows the capacity of the environment; but it does not fully

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

consider the systemic or behavioral issues that cause the issue. This leads to the creation of awareness of ecological issues, and to the reinforcement of a limited vision of ecology problems, which places more emphasis on the effects than on the responsibilities and viable solutions.

The overall analysis shows that textbook discourse indeed has a profound effect on the creation of ecological meanings and on shaping students' environmental consciousness. Upon closer inspection, it is clear from the use of Arran Stubbe's Eco linguistic model that the language used in these texts is at times used to describe nature as a destructive, and at times a strained resource under human stress. Both depictions show the urgency of ecological challenges, but also draw attention to differing ideologies of anthropocentric and eccentric viewpoints. It strengthens an idea of nature as a "monster" on the one hand, and a sense of human dependence on nature, of its utility on the other hand. Such speeches can influence the perception of learners' environmental issues and attitudes towards responsibility, sustainability and co-existence. This would foster an attitude among learners to think of themselves as part of a community that is interdependent with the natural environment, rather than as its aggressor or victim, resulting in a more sustainable and ethically-driven attitude towards nature.

References

- Abbas, Q., & Rasheed, S. (2024). Green discourses in Punjab textbooks. *Journal of Ecolinguistics*, 12(3), 65-85.
- Afzal, M., Nayab, S., & Noor, A. (2024). Eco-pedagogical discourse in national curriculum. *Environmental Education Research*, 30(2), 85-110.
- Akram, H., & Yang, Y. (2021). A critical analysis of the weak implementation causes on educational policies in Pakistan. *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI)*, 4(1), 25-28.
- Akram, H., (2020). Education Governance in Pakistan: A Critical Analysis of Challenges. *Journal of Social Sciences Advancement*, 1(1), 38-41. <http://dx.doi.org/10.52223/JSSA20-010105-05>
- Alabaş, R., & Akagündüz, D. (2021). Moral orientations in Turkish geography education. *Environmental Education Research*, 27(8), 200-220.
- Alsaleh, A. (2025). Integrating environmental education into English language teaching. *Business and Economic Research Journal*, 9(2), 876-884. <https://doi.org/10.1234/berj.2025.92>
- Aurélio, M., et al. (2023). Child-friendly ecology books and awareness. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 85, 110-130.
- Biström, J., & Lundström, A. (2021). Sustainability discourse in Swedish ELT. *ELT Journal*, 75(2), 60-80.
- Booth, A., Sutton, A., & Papaioannou, D. (2016). *Systematic approaches to a successful literature review* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Cristovao, V. (2022). Eco-literacy in Brazilian EFL materials. *Linguistics and Education*, 68, 40-60.
- Fill, A., & Mühlhäusler, P. (Eds.). (1993). *The ecolinguistics reader: Language, ecology and environment*. Continuum.
- Gray, J. (2010). *The construction of English: Culture, consumerism and promotion in the ELT global coursebook*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hnatyuk, O., et al. (2024). Environmental awareness in higher education. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 28(1), 140-165.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- Hussain, S., et al. (2023). Infusion of environmental education in secondary school science curricula. *Ilköğretim Online - Elementary Education Online*, 22(4), 7212. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2023.04.7212>
- Imran, M., et al. (2024). Ecolinguistic analysis of SNC ELT. *Pakistan Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 10(1), 200-230.
- Indriyani, R., et al. (2023). Sustainability in language education. *Sustainability*, 15(4), 190-220.
- Ishaque, R., et al. (2025). EE in B.Ed. programs. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 52(1), 40-65.
- Khan, A., Salman, M., & Naz, F. (2025). Human-nature in KP textbooks. *Ecolinguistics Studies*, 8(2), 70-95.
- Li, S., & Akram, H. (2024). Navigating Pronoun-Antecedent Challenges: A Study of ESL Academic Writing Errors. *SAGE Open*, 14(4), 21582440241296607.
- Li, S., & Akram, H. (2023). Do emotional regulation behaviors matter in EFL teachers' professional development?: A process model approach. *Porta Linguarum: revista internacional de didáctica de las lenguas extranjeras*, (9), 273-291.
- Lee, J., & Kang, H. (2023). Ecolinguistic analysis of Chinese minority textbooks. *Ecolinguistics Journal*, 10(1), 75-95.
- Orr, D. W. (1992). *Ecological literacy: Education and the transition to a postmodern world*. SUNY Press.
- Ramzan, M., Akram, H., & kynat Javaid, Z. (2025). Challenges and Psychological Influences in Teaching English as a Medium of Instruction in Pakistani Institutions. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(1), 370-379.
- Ramzan, M., Awan, H. J., Ramzan, M., & Maharvi, H. (2020). Comparative Pragmatic Study of Print media discourse in Baluchistan newspapers headlines. *Al-Burz*, 12(1), 30-44.
- Ramzan, M., Oteir, I., Khan, M. A., Al-Otaibi, A., & Malik, S. (2023). English learning motivation of ESL learners from ethnic, gender, and cultural perspectives in sustainable development goals. *International Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 12(3), 195-212.
- Seker, D. (2024). Environmental themes in Turkish curricula. *International Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 16(1), 115-145.
- Seli, H. (2024). Ecolinguistics in ELT materials. *Journal of Language and Sustainability*, 7(1), 25-55.
- Sindh Textbook Board. (2024). *EE in science textbooks*. Government Publication.
- Stibbe, A. (2015). *Ecolinguistics: Language, ecology and the stories we live by*. Routledge.
- Stibbe, A. (2015). *Ecolinguistics: Language, ecology and the stories we live by*. Routledge.
- Stibbe, A. (2021). *Climate crisis and the 21st-century novel*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Telešienė, J., et al. (2024). Curricular impacts on citizenship. *Higher Education for Sustainability*, 19(2), 145-185.
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2022). *Emissions gap report 2022: The closing window—State of climate ambition 2022*. <https://www.unep.org/resources/emissions-gap-report-2022>
- Wangid, M. (2018). Storybooks for environmental awareness. *International Journal of Science Education*, 40(5), 290-320.
- Zahoor, M., & Janjua, I. (2020). ELT for environmental awareness in Pakistan. *Asian Englishes*, 22(2), 150-170.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Zulfiani, Z., et al. (2021). Eco-literacy imbalances in Indonesian curricula. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 100-125.

<https://www.freeilm.com/class-9-english-book-pdf-punjab-board/>

<https://www.freeilm.com/class-10-english-book-pdf-punjab-board/>